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RESILIENCE AS A KEY COMPETENCE IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION – DEVELOPMENT OF A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

Engineering graduates have to cope with dynamic and complex changes and ongoing challenges that directly affect society, for which they are jointly responsible. Accordingly, engineering education requires competencies that enable future engineers to create adaptive systems that are capable of dealing with crises and sudden disruptions. These abilities are generally referred to as resilience. The purpose of this study was to develop a conceptual framework to define and categorize resilience-related competencies in engineering education, such as flexibility, adaptability or dealing with uncertainty. Based on this framework, the extent to which resilience-related competencies are considered necessary in existing frameworks and in engineering education research can be explored.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Given the fact that climate change increases the frequency of natural disasters such as floods and hurricanes, concern about global risks is increasing and there is a great demand for sustainable, interdisciplinary solutions. Likewise, there is an agreement that risk analysis alone is not sufficient to protect threatened infrastructures from emerging disruptive events [1, 2]. Instead, those require solutions which also increase preparedness for response and recovery. This discourse is frequently summarized under resilience, which describes a system's ability to cope with sudden disturbances, to learn from them and to be adaptive.

As engineering “is a collaborative, complex activity that demands socio-technical, societal and systems perspective” [3], graduates have to cope with dynamic changes, challenges and ongoing complex problems that directly affect society, for which they are jointly responsible. Thus, there is a need for more detailed description of competencies engineering graduates should have which goes beyond basic technological knowledge and skills and also focuses on adaptation to change and complexity [3, 4].

The growing discourse on future skills of engineers often focuses on the relevance of competencies for sustainable development [5, 6]. Less in the foreground, however, are competencies that enable the handling of sudden disruptions or disasters, such as the abovementioned, earthquakes or wildfires, and the associated responsibility of engineers (see e.g. the literature review by Beagon et al. [7]). In their study on engineering habits of mind, Lucas and Hanson [8] identified resilience as one “learning habit of mind” of engineers. At the same time, studies with students showed that there are less knowledge and understanding of the relevance of resilience in context of engineering [4, 9-11]. Accordingly, Baytiyeh and Kaja [11], for example, are explicitly calling for more awareness on dealing with crises within engineering education, as engineers are jointly responsible for mitigation strategies with regard to earthquakes. With regard to competence-oriented teaching and learning as well as the integration of resilience into engineering education, however, it is first necessary to clearly define the concept of resilience and the associated relevant competencies.

For this purpose, we propose a conceptual framework, the development of which is presented in this paper. The framework is derived from theory to define and categorize resilience-related competencies in engineering education, such as flexibility, adaptability or dealing with uncertainty. Furthermore, we show how this framework can be applied on existing frameworks, such as the CDIO Syllabus.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Definitions of Resilience

Growing discourses, definitions and publications regarding resilience have emerged in the last years. Resilience finds application in several disciplines, like ecology, psychology, geography or engineering. Holling [12] shaped the discourse by studying the behavior of ecosystems with respect to sudden disturbances. Building on this, resilience has evolved as an approach to study and understand complex adaptive systems and their behavior in response to (surprising) perturbations [13, 14]. As socio-ecological systems, like cities, are characterized by many interactions of people and their environment, complexity and change are inherent to these systems. Folke et al. [15] identified four factors which characterize resilience in socio-ecological systems: learning to live with change and uncertainty, nurturing diversity in its various forms, combining different types of knowledge for learning and creating opportunity for self-organization and cross-scale linkages. Moreover, it is important to differentiate between resilience and robustness or persistence to disturbances. “[Resilience] is also about the opportunities that disturbance opens up in terms of recombination of evolved structures and processes, renewal of the system and emergence of new trajectories. In this sense, resilience provides adaptive capacity that allow for continuous development, like a dynamic adaptive interplay between sustaining and developing with change.” [16] Accordingly, resilience is a dynamic concept based on interdisciplinary thinking and perspectives.

With regard to engineered, or socio-technical systems, the concept was expanded to “resilience engineering”, especially by Hollnagel [1, 17]. Typically understood as an exercise in problem solving, engineering design focuses on optimization of systems with regard to “known information in pursuit of maximum efficiency” [2]. In contrast to socio-ecological systems, engineered systems are based on direct human invention and construction, they are accordingly directly subject to human influence and control. Urban systems, for example, based on infrastructure and buildings, are created and maintained to provide a service to society [2].

Hollnagel [1, 17] defined four key abilities which are relevant for building resilience engineering: Responding to regular and irregular disruptions (knowing what to do – addressing the actual), monitoring which is or can become a threat in the near term (knowing what to look for – addressing the critical), learning from experience, both successes as well as failures (knowing what to expect – addressing the potential) and anticipating developments, threats and opportunities further into the future, such as potential changes, disruptions, pressures and their consequences (knowing what has happened – addressing the factual). Park et al. [2] refined these abilities as sensing, anticipation, adaptation and learning. Both approaches describe properties or abilities a resilient engineered system at least should have.

Both the socio-ecological and the socio-technical approach are illustrated especially by urban systems, as they are characterized by multiple socio-ecological and socio-technical interactions. Infrastructure, mobility or buildings are based on engineering work which directly affects people living in the respective urban area. The discourse about resilience in urban systems is called as “urban resilience”, which “refers to the ability of an urban system-and all its constituent socio-ecological and socio-technical networks across temporal and spatial scales-to maintain or rapidly return to desired functions in the face of a disturbance, to adapt to change, and to quickly transform systems that limit current or future adaptive capacity.” [18] This definition, based on a broad literature review by Meerow et al. [18], shows the dynamic approach of resilience as well as the multiple pathways to resilience.

In summary, all understandings of resilience or definitions have the following aspects in common: we consider the occurrence of a threat or disturbance, we consider systems trying to cope with that disturbance and we analyze mechanisms or capabilities (coping strategies) for how systems learn from those disturbances to provide adaptive capacity [see also 14].

2.2 Resilience-related Competencies

As resilience always describes the ability of a system to cope with disturbances, there are several concrete sub-competencies which go along with this. In their broad literature review, Francis and Bekera [19] summarized several abilities which were characterized by different definitions of resilience. These can help to divide the dynamic and sometimes complex definitions into single sub-competencies, a resilient system or individual should possess. To give a brief overview, those resilience-based competencies are for example: the ability to anticipate, to absorb, to adapt, to recover, to recognize unanticipated perturbations, to cope with stress, to response, to withstand or in general also flexibility. As mentioned before, these properties are not the same as robustness, because resilience is especially about the opportunities inherent to change, as it provides adaptive capacity for continuous development [14, 16].

Since the above definitions and key aspects regarding resilience are not all listed in the literature review by Francis and Bekera [19], the following table will serve as an illustration of how competencies for resilience can be derived from theoretical concepts.

Table 1. Examples of resilience-related competencies derived from theoretical concepts

Socio-ecological resilience	Competencies
[15, 16]	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Dealing with change- Dealing with uncertainty- Promoting diversity- Interdisciplinary thinking

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning - Self-organization - Adaptive capacity
Resilience Engineering	Competencies
[1, 2, 17]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responding to disruptions - Monitoring of threats - Sensing - Learning - Anticipating - Adapting
Urban Resilience	Competencies
[18]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adapting to change - Transforming

3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The purpose of this study was to develop a conceptual framework for defining and characterizing resilience-related competencies in engineering education. This framework is based on two steps: At first, resilience-related competencies were compiled. For this, several definitions of resilience were surveyed with regards to their underlying competencies. One option was shown through the literature review by Francis and Bekera [19], which was described in the theory section. Based on this step, the identified resilience-related competencies were categorized in order to specify their relevance to resilience, as it is not always clear to what extent individual competencies actually address resilience.

The authors recommend a division of resilience-related competencies into subcategories “Specific-Resilience” (SR), “General-Resilience” (GR) and “No Relevance” (NO). These are based on the following rules:

- (1) Specific-Resilience: This category includes competencies that are inherent to the idea of resilience, as described in the theory section, such as “dealing with uncertainty” or “to recognize unanticipated perturbations”. The competencies in this category can be described as sufficient for characterizing resilience.
- (2) General-Resilience: This category includes all competencies that are linked to resilience, like “system-thinking” or “problem solving”, but only implicitly deal with it. However, these may be necessary preconditions for practical application of resilience.
- (3) No Relevance: Here, we consider competencies that do not have specific relevance to resilience, like “teamwork”. This category is only relevant when

deductively assigning all competencies, as we, for example, do with regards to the CDIO Syllabus.

The second step, categorizing resilience-related competencies, presents the most significant challenge. There are some competencies that are considered relevant in the context of engineering education and also address resilience, but do not necessarily characterize resilience on their own. This is the case, for example, with “problem solving” or “system-thinking”. In general, problem solving is a key attribute of engineers, but problem solving alone does not necessarily entail resilience.

Based on these steps, the framework was exemplarily applied using an excerpt of the CDIO Syllabus, which is explained below. By applying it to existing frameworks, it is possible to examine the extent to which resilience-related competencies are considered relevant for engineers.

The engineering education initiative CDIO (Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate) has developed a Syllabus of knowledge, skills and attitudes engineers should acquire [5, 20]. By comparison to other standards, such as the European EUR-ACE® framework standards for accreditation of engineering programs or the American Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET) criteria, it was found that an engineering program based on the Syllabus would also meet other standards [5, 20]. Thus, we take the CDIO Syllabus and in excerpts its second section dealing with personal and professional skills as an example for the third step of the conceptual framework. The following table shows an exemplary application of the categorization of resilience-related competencies.

Table 2. Examples for categorization of resilience-based competencies in CDIO Syllabus – excerpt from chapter 2.1–2.4

Personal and professional skills and attributes	Category
Problem Identification and Formulation	GR
Modeling	GR
Estimation and Qualitative Analysis	SR
Analysis with Uncertainty	SR
Thinking Holistically	SR
Emergence and Interactions in Systems	SR
Initiative and the Willingness to Make Decisions in the Face of Uncertainty	SR
Creative Thinking	GR
Critical Thinking	GR
Professional Behavior	NO

The assignment to the resilience categories is also associated with a number of difficulties. The description and interpretation of competencies is often not uniform, so

that the same competence may be meant but formulated differently [6]. For example, the CDIO Syllabus is divided into chapters and categories. One category is described as “System Thinking” (2.3) with further sub-competencies like “Emergence and Interactions in Systems”. Here, it is questionable to what extent the assignment to resilience should be made based on the higher-level chapter or the more detailed lower-level competencies.

Further, biases cannot be ruled out in the classification into “specific” and “general” resilience. Others would perhaps assign “system thinking” to “specific resilience”. Therefore, it is of central importance to define resilience-related competencies uniformly, in order to be able to establish a framework for their characterization.

Applying this framework then to existing ones, such as CDIO, EUR-ACE, ABET, or even specifically to specific study program outcomes, it is thus possible to determine the extent to which resilience-related competencies are considered relevant in engineering education.

4 CONCLUSIONS

As engineering graduates will have to cope with increasing change and complex problems, competencies are needed which go beyond pure technical knowledge [3]. One possible approach can be described by resilience thinking in order to promote dealing with change and uncertainty with regard to creating resilient systems.

In this paper, relevant definitions of resilience were presented. Based on this, examples were given of how these can be divided into categories with regard to the relevance of resilience in order to be able to classify them in existing frameworks, such as the CDIO Syllabus. On the one hand, this framework can be used to examine existing frameworks or research with regard to resilience-based competencies in order to determine to what extent these are considered relevant in the context of engineering education. Furthermore, the framework can be a starting point for the implementation of these competencies in engineering curricula.

Ongoing research regarding to what extent resilience competencies are already discussed in engineering education research is based upon this framework. A next and ongoing step is to screen diploma supplements of different engineering programs at European Universities to investigate whether and how these competencies are already implemented in engineering education. On the one hand, this makes it possible to examine what relevance resilience-related competencies currently have in these study programs. Here, first of all, it must be qualitatively examined to what extent the already existing resilience-related competencies are used directly or indirectly, i.e. to what extent resilience is actually implied with these competencies. On the other hand, the results of the analysis of the diploma supplements can have implications for

the universities. By applying the framework, gaps can be made visible and curricula can be further developed with regard to resilience-related competencies.

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